

Influence of Different Pre-Sowing Treatments on Seedling Emergence of *Acacia Auriculiformis*

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Abstract

Acacia auriculiformis, a multi-purpose tree is highly valued for its floricultural importance and other general uses throughout the whole world. This study assessed emergence percentage and emergence rate of *A.auriculiformis*. Viable seeds determined by floatation method were sown in white plastic buckets filled with loose, sieved and well drained river sand at a sowing depth of 3cm. Bucket diameter was 22cm and bucket depth from base to the brim was 24cm. Four(4) replicates of 100 randomly picked seeds at 25 seeds per bucket was used for each treatment and the buckets were laid out in a Complete Randomised Design(CRD). The seeds were subjected to pre-sowing treatments using 98% concentrated Sulphuric acid, hot water(wet heat), physical abrasion for 1,2 and 3 minutes and control experiment. Data were subjected to statistical analysis. Results showed wet heat (hot water) treatment with highest emergence of 63 to 87 % and a mean emergence time of 22 to 24 days, while comparatively control experiment gave 72 % emergence and mean emergence time of 24 days.

Keywords: *Acacia Auriculiformis*, Pre-sowing Treatments, Emergence Percentage, Emergence Rate

Introduction

Acacia auriculiformis Cunn ex Benth., is an ever-green tree belonging to the Angiospermae Group, Order Fabales, Family Fabaceae (Synonym Leguminosae) and Sub-Family Mimosoideae. *Acacia* Mill., genus consist of about 800 tropical and sub-tropical species of mostly trees, also shrubby *Acacia* species exist (Willis & Airyshaw, 1973). Common English names of *A. auriculiformis* include Ear leaf Acacia, Earpod, Earpod wattle, Northern black wattle and Tan wattle. Etymologically, the generic name is derived from Greek meaning sharp points, spines or thorns but *Acacia auriculiformis* is an un-armed or spineless *Acacia*, while the specific epithet *auriculiformis* refer to the ear shaped form of its leaves or phyllodes. The tree is native to Australia, Indonesia and Papau New Guinea but now adapted to tropical, frost free, humid and sub-humid climates of the World.(Turnbull,1986).

A.auriculiformis is a moderately sized tree reaching up to 15-30metres with dense foliage, bark smooth in young trees, becoming grey or brownish black, rough and longitudinally fissured with age. Leaf stalks are modified into flattened blade called

phyllode which are narrowly oblong, slightly curved or falcate (sickle shaped), 11 to 20 cm long. Flowers yellow, fragrant or sweet scented, crowded in axillary spikes, 8 to 9 cm long. Fruit pods are bright green while young but hard or woody and much coiled or twisted, turning brown on ripening, their brownish-black seeds hang on string like orange arils serving to attract birds for their dispersal.

The tree is economically important and highly valued for its floricultural importance and priced in landscaping for shade and ornamental purposes in urban areas, their flowers are a source of pollen for honey production, the tree has been used satisfactorily as nurse tree in plantations in Asia. The wood makes attractive furniture, useful for carvings and for construction works, also used as fuel wood, it gives excellent charcoal that glows well and burns without smoking and sparking, wood fibre useful in pulp and paper industry, also water soluble tannin is present in its bark for processing animal hides or leather.

One pertinent question in the field of seed germination biology and dormancy studies is what actually controls the timing of seed germination. Many factors such as levels of carbon dioxide, improper aeration, diseases, pests, nature of growth medium and presence of allelo-chemicals have been suggested as being capable of preventing germination (Holm, 1979). However, in many leguminous seeds, hard seed coats prevent imbibition of water and exchange of gases, thus preventing initiation of the germination process (Maguire, 1975).

A healthy seed that does not germinate after providing it with the necessary conditions for germination is said to be in a dormant state (Lawal, 2004). Dormancy is the condition of seed when it fails to germinate because of internal conditions, even though external conditions of light, temperature, sufficient oxygen, disease free soil and moisture are favourable (Osonubi & Chukwuka, 1999). According to Baskin and Baskin (2004), dormancy is when seeds are unable to germinate in a specific period of time under a combination of environmental factors that are normally favourable for germination.

Any treatment which reduces or destroys seed impermeability by weakening or softening the seed coat is known as scarification. Scarification treatments soften the seed coat in order to make the seed coat permeable to water and gases without destroying the embryo (Seedbrock, 2006). Methods used to artificially break down seed coat dormancy includes scarification with sand paper, emery cloth, concentrated Sulphuric acid and other acids, addition of organic solvents such as acetone, alcohols and carbon disulphide, wet heat (hot water), cutting, drilling, filing, nicking or treatment of seeds with objects such as pins, razor blade, knife or even cutlass. In some cases, plant hormones, oven or dry heat treatments which is analogous to heating by vegetation fires (Martins *et al* 1975).

The aim of the experiment is to break or over-come seed coat dormancy towards enhanced multiplication of *A. auriculiformis* for its decorative value and other general uses.

Materials and Methods

Source of Seeds

Seeds of *A.auriculiformis* used for the experiment were sourced from Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko Main Campus.(Latitude 4° and 13° N, Longitude 2° N and 15° E,Altitude 369 metres above sea level) Ondo State, Nigeria.

Study Site and Management

The study was conducted at the Screen House of the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria for a period of 50 days. Seeds were sown in perforated, white plastic buckets filled with loose and well drained river sand, the buckets were laid out in a Complete Randomised Design (CRD). Four (4) replicates of 100 randomly picked seeds at 25 seeds per bucket were used for each treatment at sowing depth of 3metres.

Seed Viability Test

The floating method of Pandey & Sinha (2010)was used to test for seed viability. The process involved dipping the seeds in a beaker filled with water, seeds that floated were discarded, while seeds that sank to the bottom of the beaker were regarded as viable and were used for the experiment.

Dormancy Studies

Seeds for the experiment were subjected to 98% concentrated Sulphuric acid, wet heat(hot water),physical abrasion and control experiment at 100 seeds each for four(4) replications at 25seeds per bucket and then sown.

Acid treatment

A total of 98% Concentrated Sulphuric acid was poured on the seeds and stirred for 1,2 and 3minutes.The acid was decanted and the seeds were rinsed several times in distilled water and then sown.

Wet Heat (Hot Water) Treatment

Boiled water at 100 was poured on the seeds and stirred for varying time durations of 1,2 and 3minutes and then sown.

Physical Abrasion Treatment

Seeds were manually or physically abraded with rough sand paper on all sides for varying time durations of 1, 2 and 3minutes and then sown.

Control experiment

One hundred (100) un-treated seeds were sown as control.

Emergence counts

The number of days taken for individual seed to emerge was recorded. Duration of the experiment was 50days.

Emergence Percentage

Germination percentage was recorded as the ratio of the number of seeds that emerged to the total number of seeds sown and was multiplied by 100.

$$\text{Emergence percentage} = \frac{\text{Total number of seeds that emerged}}{\text{Total number of seeds sown}} \times 100$$

Table 1: Standard Error of the Seed Pre-Treatments on *A.auriculiformis*

DURATION/ TYPE OF TES	SULPHURIC ACID	BOILING	PHYSICAL SCARIFICATION
1 MIN	1.46 ± 1.78	8.33 ± 6.54	1.30 ± 1.23
2 MIN	0.53 ± 1.25	10.53 ± 4.72	1.16 ± 1.65
3 MIN	0.79 ± 1.20	9.33 ± 4.98	0.96 ± 1.33
CONTROL	4.24 ± 2.978		

Figure1: Effect of pre-sowing treatments on emergence percentage of *Acacia auriculiformis*

Figure 2: Effect of different pre treatments on germination rate of *A.auriculiformis*

Discussion

Breaking or over-coming dormancy in legumes using concentrated Sulphuric acid, wet heat (boiled or hot water), oven (dry heat), plant hormones, physical abrasion and by other methods have been demonstrated by Ajiboye & Agboola (2010); Ajiboye *et al* (2011); Missanjo *et al* (2014); Wen *et al* (2024).

Copeland (1979) and Egle (1989) reported that hard seed coat created barriers to water uptake and entry of gases and that the presence of continuous layers of tightly packed cells in the seed coat constitute a barrier to gases and water imbibition.

Wen *et al* (2024) states that the palisade layer of most leguminous seeds are composed of macro sclereid cells with thick secondary walls and they are impermeable to water because of presence of hydrophobic substances such as cutin, lignin, pectin, quinones, suberin and wax. 2 minutes wet heat pre-treatment gave highest seedling emergence percentage of 87% and also had a fast mean germination time of 6 days. Acid pre-treatment gave results of 18 to 62% and fast mean germination times of 5 to 7 days. Physical scarification pre-treatment gave emergence of 41 to 57%. Treatments control gave seedling emergence of 72% and mean germination time of 24 days.

More enhanced breaking of dormancy by wet heat pre-treatments (63 to 87%) may explain how moist heat resulting from burning of dry vegetation that precedes the planting season helps to overcome seed coat dormancy in the soil.

Recommendation

The findings showed that 1, 2 and 3 minutes wet heat pre-treatment methods with results of 63, 81 and 87% are best recommended for prolific propagation of *A. auriculiformis* for its decorative value and other general uses. Thus, there should be massive efforts towards propagating *A.auriculiformis* for its aesthetic value.

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